

Educational Technology for Teaching & Learning and Grade 7 Students' Proficiency Skills in Science & Technology

John Vincent C. Aliazas

Master of Arts in Science and Technology, Laguna State Polytechnic University

johnvincent.aliazas@lspu.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

This study focused on examining the relationship between educational technology and the proficiency skills of grade 7 students in science and technology in selected schools within the division of San Pablo City. The study included a total of 116 science curriculum students from secondary schools in the division. The researcher utilized Pearson correlation to determine significant relationships between variables. The findings indicated that educational technology-related factors, particularly instructional learning materials, were seldom used. However, respondents highlighted that teacher methodology played a crucial role in students' performance. The respondents expressed agreement that educational technology could help them achieve higher performance in science and technology. In terms of the teaching-learning domains of practice, the respondents perceived the design of educational technology tools as effective, but improvements were needed in their development and utilization. Utilization of these materials was reported to be almost never used. Integrated media was highly prioritized by students to achieve better marks in the subject. These results suggest that the use of educational technology may enhance students' performance in science and technology. The respondents demonstrated advanced proficiency skills in terms of knowledge and process/skills, while their level of understanding was marked as proficient. Furthermore, a significant relationship was found between student proficiency skills and educational technology-related factors, particularly instructional learning materials and attitudes towards science and technology. However, except for the subdomains of utilization and management, no significant relationship was observed between the teaching-learning domains of practice and students' proficiency skills. In conclusion, this study highlights the limited use of instructional learning materials and the importance of teacher methodology in students' performance. It also underscores the potential of educational technology in enhancing students' performance in science and technology. The findings emphasize the significance of incorporating effective instructional materials and cultivating positive attitudes towards science and technology. Additionally, the study suggests the need to improve the utilization and management of educational technology tools.

Keywords: *Educational Technology, Science Proficiency Skills, Grade 7 Science.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the field of education, one of the primary goals is to prepare students for life and nurture them into productive and responsible citizens. Educators often refer to this process as lifelong learning, which requires the holistic development of learners. Schools strive to employ various teaching and learning tools to enhance the quality of education. The use of multimedia technology has proven to be an effective approach in this regard. Research has demonstrated that innovative computer-based tools significantly

improve the acquisition of skills and performance necessary to thrive in a complex, technologically advanced, knowledge-based economy (McMahon et al., 2004; Psarras, 2006).

Information aids and multimedia have become integral parts of daily school activities. Both teachers and students need to adapt to the demands of these technological advancements in education. However, some misconceptions exist regarding technology, with concerns that it may eventually replace classroom teachers (Boekaerts & Corno, 2005; Njenga & Fourie, 2010). It is important to understand that technology should be seen as a tool that complements and enhances the teaching and learning process, rather than replacing human educators (Alexander et al., 2004; McGarr, 2009). Technology has now become integrated into schools, allowing students to have greater involvement in the learning process. The increased use of computers in education has brought notable changes to traditional teaching methods (Bennett et al., 2008). Computer literacy has become one of the fundamental skills, and students now learn how to use computers to retrieve information, process data, and develop logical thinking skills (Wallace & Clariana, 2005).

Multimedia technology has gained popularity in classroom instruction as it accelerates learning and enhances knowledge retention (Neo & Neo, 2004; Hoffman et al., 2013). Modern educational technologies such as computers, LCD projectors, interactive boards, and tablet PCs aid learners in developing various skills by providing them with relevant and engaging information. The judicious use of technology is expected to improve the quality of teaching and learning (Grunwald & Corsbie-Massay, 2006). The researcher recognizes the vital role of technology in enriching the learning experience across all domains. Therefore, the researcher has investigated the effects of educational technology on teaching and learning outcomes, aiming to understand how technology can positively impact education.

Technology is often seen as a solution to address failures and deficiencies. It has the potential to drive progress and is synonymous with modernization, growth, and development in developed countries (Brooks et al., 2009). However, developing countries like the Philippines face numerous challenges, particularly in the education sector. Disappointing statistics such as high dropout rates (15% in high school), low school achievement rates (66% in elementary), poor board examination passing rates (below 50%), and high unemployment rates (60% for new graduates) indicate that there are significant shortcomings in accessibility and quality within the Philippine educational system (DepEd).

The fast-changing world and emerging trends in education have left the Philippines' educational system in crisis. While the use of technology is being accepted and embraced by many Filipino educators, traditional teaching methods still dominate (Zajda & Gibbs, 2009). Teachers often take the lead in the learning process, leaving students ill-equipped to adapt to these changes. Traditional instructional materials such as handwritten lectures on manila paper or posters and hand-drawn illustrations still find their place in some classroom discussions. These traditional methods may limit students' opportunities for deeper learning.

One significant change in education is the increased use of computers and other devices as tools in the learning process and instructional delivery (Morrison & Lowther, 2010). This reflects how technology is used in workplaces and homes. Technology tools such as word processing, desktop publishing, databases, spreadsheets, drawing, painting, and graphing programs have become essential for learners (Eisenberg, 2010). Students now use these tools to construct written compositions, use on-screen calculators or graphing programs, manipulate data in spreadsheets, search for information in databases,

or publish school papers. Video, sound, and multimedia equipment have also become valuable tools for enhancing the teaching and learning process (Anderson & Maninger, 2007).

Currently, digital technologies for communication are becoming commonplace, and teachers no longer have to rely solely on traditional textbooks to transfer knowledge. Teachers need to incorporate these new trends into their everyday classroom activities by utilizing digital technology in the learning process (Krumsvik, 2008; Lim et al., 2013). They also have a responsibility to raise students' awareness of the importance of change and innovation, even within the four corners of the classroom, and to emphasize that these devices are not merely quick answer retrieval systems but unique tools to explore different ways of solving problems and using multimedia and internet resources effectively.

Educational technology in the Philippines has gained recognition, and various initiatives on the use of technology in education have been designed and implemented. Lamb (2006) emphasized the importance of integrating technology into the teaching and learning environment to prepare students for life in the 21st century. Educators and students can activate their learning environment through the effective use of technology.

This study focuses on students' perceptions of the effects of educational technology instruction on teaching and learning Science and Technology lessons. The curriculum of educational technology programs in selected secondary schools in San Pablo City is the focus, considering the changes in technology as tools and systems for educational purposes.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this study on educational technology for teaching and learning, the researchers adopted the theory of Instructional Theory and Technology by Charles M. Reigeluth (2012) and the Theory of Practice by the Association for Educational Communications and Technology (AECT, 2013). Instructional theory and technology encompasses the theory and practice of utilizing, designing, managing, evaluating, and developing processes and resources for education. It goes beyond software, hardware, and internet applications, focusing on improving human abilities, particularly academic achievement in the teaching and learning process. This theory aims to transform educational and training systems from ones that sort students to ones that maximize learning, shifting from time-based progress to attainment-based progress.

Reigeluth (2012) presents a holistic vision of the new paradigm of instruction, characterized by core ideas such as learning-focused and learner-centered approaches, learning by doing, attainment-based progress, customized instruction, criterion-referenced testing, collaborative learning, and enjoyable learning experiences. He further proposes a vision of instruction that outlines task and instructional spaces, team and individual assessment, instructional strategies for the task space, and instructional strategies for the instructional space. On the other hand, the Association for Educational Communications and Technology (AECT, 2013) defines educational technology as the study and ethical practice of facilitating learning and improving performance through the creation, use, and management of appropriate technological processes and resources.

AECT describes the field of educational technology as consisting of five interrelated domains: design, development, utilization, management, and evaluation. Each domain includes sub-domains that provide further description and specialization within the field. The domains have a synergistic relationship, and research can focus on one or several domains, or even combine functions across domains. Each domain

contributes to the others, as well as to the research and theory shared within the broader educational technology field.

By adopting these theories, the researchers in this study aimed to explore the effects of educational technology instruction on teaching and learning Science and Technology lessons, considering the principles of instructional theory and technology as well as the domains and sub-domains of educational technology outlined by AECT.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researcher employed a descriptive correlational design, which aims to describe data and characteristics of the population or phenomenon under investigation. The distinguishing feature of correlation studies is the attempt to estimate a relationship between variables, moving beyond simple descriptive research (Hetland & Winner, 2004). Given that this study focuses on the perceived effects of educational technology for teaching and learning, as well as students' proficiency skills performance in Science and Technology, a descriptive correlational design is appropriate.

The respondents for the study were selected from secondary schools in the division of San Pablo City during the academic year 2013-2014. Out of the fourteen public schools in the division, three schools that specialize in science curriculum were chosen, and a total of 116 students from these schools participated in the study. A survey questionnaire was utilized as the main data-gathering tool to measure the domains of practice related to educational technology. The research instrument consisted of three major parts.

Part I collected information on the personal profile of the respondents. Part II obtained responses from the respondents regarding educational technology-related factors, focusing on instructional learning materials, teacher's methodology, and students' attitudes. Part III gathered responses on the perceived effects of educational technology on different domains of practice in teaching the subject of Science and Technology. These domains included design, development, utilization, management, and evaluation. Additionally, an achievement test was administered to measure the proficiency level of the students in Science and Technology. The test covered 2 units and 10 lessons during the second grading period.

To ensure the content validity and reliability of the instrument, it was reviewed by five experts in the field of education. The corrections and suggestions provided by the experts were incorporated into the final refinement of the instrument. Frequency count and percentage distribution were used to describe the profile of the respondents and determine the grade average of the students in Science and Technology.

Weighted mean and standard deviation were employed to determine the students' perception of the effects of educational technology-related factors on teaching and students' performance. Furthermore, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to investigate the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents, related factors, domains of practice, and proficiency skills performance in Science and Technology. The hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Demographic		f	%
Sex	Male	50	43.1
	Female	66	56.9
Age	12	53	45.7
	13	56	48.3
	14	7	6.0
Father's Educational Attainment	Elementary Undergraduate	2	1.7
	Elementary Graduate	1	0.9
	High School Undergraduate	4	3.4
	High School Graduate	18	15.5
	College Undergraduate	24	20.7
	College Graduate	67	57.8
Mother's Educational Attainment	Elementary Undergraduate	1	0.9
	Elementary Graduate	2	1.7
	High School Undergraduate	2	1.7
	High School Graduate	27	23.3
	College Undergraduate	14	12.1
	College Graduate	70	60.3
Father's Occupation	Recyclable Waste Collector	2	1.7
	Vendor	6	5.2
	Driver	22	19
	Laborer	12	10.3
	Construction Worker	6	5.2
	Merchandiser	8	6.9
	Electrician	21	18.1
	Teacher	8	6.9
	Nurse	5	4.3
	Doctor	4	3.4
	Others	22	19
Mother's Occupation	Housewife	43	40.2
	Vendor	3	2.8
	Laundry woman	5	4.7
	Housemaid	5	4.7
	Laborer	7	6.5
	Tailor	3	2.8
	Saleslady	3	2.8
	Teacher	15	14
	Nurse	4	3.7
	Doctor	2	1.9
	Others	17	15.9
Family Income	Php 7,000 & below	18	15.5
	Php 7,001-12,000	24	20.7
	Php 12,001-16,000	18	15.5
	Php 16,001-21,000	11	9.5
	Php 21,001-25,000	14	12.1
	Php 25,001 & above	31	26.7

N: 116

Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the demographic characteristics of the respondents, highlighting their personal backgrounds. The data collected in this study shed light on various aspects of the respondents' profiles, revealing interesting patterns and trends.

According to the findings, 56.9% of the respondents were female, indicating a slightly higher representation of females within the sample. Among these females, the majority (48.3%) were 13 years old, suggesting that this age group was the most prevalent among the female respondents.

Moreover, the study examined the educational background of the respondents' parents. It was found that a significant proportion of the respondents had parents who were college graduates. Specifically, 57.8% of the female respondents' parents and 60.3% of the male respondents' parents had obtained a college degree. This suggests a relatively high level of educational attainment among the parents of the surveyed individuals.

The employment status of the respondents' fathers was also investigated. The results indicated that 19% of the fathers worked as drivers, implying that this occupation was relatively common among the male respondents' fathers. On the other hand, the study revealed that 40.2% of the mothers were classified as housewives, suggesting that a substantial proportion of the female respondents' mothers dedicated their time primarily to domestic responsibilities.

Furthermore, the researchers examined the family income of the respondents. The findings indicated that 26.7% of the participants belonged to households with a family income of Php 25,001 and above. This suggests that a significant portion of the respondents came from families with relatively higher income levels.

In summary, Table 1 provides a detailed overview of the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their personal backgrounds. The data highlights the representation of females, the age distribution among female respondents, the educational background of the parents, the employment status of the fathers, and the family income levels. These findings offer valuable insights for further analysis and interpretation in the context of the study.

Table 2. Perceived Educational Technology Related Factors

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Instructional Learning Materials	2.97	0.39	Seldom
Teacher's Methodology	4.01	0.34	Often
Students' Attitude	3.88	0.48	Agree

Table 2 presents the findings regarding the perceptions of the respondents on various factors related to educational technology. The results provide valuable insights into the utilization and availability of educational technology learning materials in the classroom, as well as the teachers' methodologies and the students' attitudes towards science and technology.

The findings suggest that the respondents reported seldom using educational technology learning materials in the classroom. However, they perceived that these materials were available within the classroom setting. This may indicate that the usage of instructional learning materials among grade 7 student-respondents from public schools in San Pablo City could potentially be influenced by the accessibility of these materials, the teachers' ability to facilitate their use, and the students' skills in

effectively utilizing them. During the researcher's visit, it was observed that the educational technology facilities and devices were readily available for use. In fact, one of the selected schools even provided each student with a personal computer tablet sponsored by the local government, highlighting the commitment to integrating technology into the learning process.

Regarding teacher methodology, it was perceived that teachers utilized varied media in their teaching, including video clips, tapes, and movie strips. The teachers instructed students to report or present individual or group activities using multimedia presentations. Additionally, students were given the freedom to choose their preferred media for presenting projects. This aligns with the idea that modern teaching methods emphasize student-centered approaches and promote interactive learning experiences. However, despite the availability of modern teaching methods and materials, the findings suggest that teachers tended to rely more on traditional teaching methods. This could be attributed to factors such as heavy academic workloads, which may make it challenging for teachers to adequately prepare and implement educational technology materials.

Lastly, the findings demonstrated a strong manifestation of positive indicators regarding students' attitudes towards science and technology. Many of the students were familiar with a variety of multimedia or educational technology devices used in the classroom, and they expressed a willingness to learn and utilize these tools for a more interactive and enhanced learning experience. This finding aligns with the work of Sanchez & Hueros (2010), which suggests that technology serves as a motivating factor for students. The use of educational technology in the classroom can increase student participation and, consequently, lead to significant improvements in academic performance (Morrison & Lowther, 2010). These findings highlight a positive correlation between the integration of technology and student motivation, engagement, and participation in the learning process.

In summary, Table 2 provides insights into the perceptions of the respondents regarding educational technology-related factors. The findings reveal the availability and utilization of educational technology learning materials, the teachers' methodologies, and the students' attitudes towards science and technology. These findings contribute to the understanding of the current state of educational technology integration in the classroom and offer valuable implications for further research and improvement in teaching practices.

Table 3. Perceived Educational Technology Domains of Practice

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Design	4.01	0.55	Effective
Development	3.48	0.84	Agree
Utilization	2.38	0.69	Almost Never
Management	3.69	1.01	Highly Priority
Evaluation	3.15	0.55	Somewhat True of Me

Table 3 provides an overview of the respondents' perceptions regarding educational technology in relation to different domains of practice. The findings reveal insights into the effectiveness of design, the encouragement of technology use, the utilization of educational technology in the classroom, the management of technology, the desire for access to instructional materials, and the evaluation of new technologies.

In terms of design, the findings suggest that the respondents perceived it to be effective. This aligns with the notion that internet knowledge is essential for both students and teachers (Bangert, 2004). Students are comfortable using the internet and can access substantial information, which enhances their learning experiences (Eisnberg et al., 2010).

Regarding the development domain of practice, the respondents agreed that there is encouragement for the use of educational technology in the classrooms. Kraut (2013) propose that handheld devices can replace heavy and cumbersome textbooks, providing students with access to vast amounts of information and resources. This is supported by Burns (2013), who argue that mobile computing has significant potential for technology integration and can foster student creativity and engagement in learning activities. However, the success of implementing a handheld program depends on proper planning, preparation, and research.

The findings indicate that the utilization of educational technology in the classroom was almost never observed. This may be attributed to the fear of damaging the devices, the high cost of maintenance if they malfunction, or limited teacher knowledge and preference for conventional instructional methods. Reigeluth (2012) emphasizes that changes in teaching and learning are essential prerequisites for effective technology integration. Nevertheless, using integrated media for presentations allows teachers to bring the world to the classroom, enhancing students' learning experiences.

Management of educational technology emerged as a high priority according to the respondents. Brooks (2009) notes that instructional technology as a classroom tool for improving curriculum and instruction is still relatively unproven. While there is potential, workshops, and ideas, there are few actual implementations (Grunwald & Corsbie-Massay, 2006). Apprehensions regarding the impact on instruction quality and student learning can only be addressed through objective examination of test cases.

The respondents highly prioritized having access to the aforementioned educational technology materials. They are exposed to them, have easy access, and are familiar with their functions in their student lives. Grade 7 students expressed a desire for these instructional learning materials to improve their academic performance.

Finally, in terms of evaluation, the findings indicate that respondents were somewhat skeptical of new technologies and only used them when necessary. They expressed a love for new technologies and a desire to be the first to experience and use them. They believed that educational technology could actively involve them in classroom activities.

In summary, Table 3 presents the respondents' perceptions regarding educational technology across different domains of practice. The findings highlight the effectiveness of design, the encouragement for technology use, the limited utilization of educational technology in the classroom, the importance of technology management, the desire for access to instructional materials, and the somewhat skeptical evaluation of new technologies. These perceptions provide valuable insights for understanding the current state of educational technology integration and can inform future efforts to enhance teaching and learning practices.

Table 4. Respondents' Level of Science and Technology Proficiency Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Remarks
Knowledge	90.26	3.82	Advanced
Process/Skills	90.30	4.47	Advanced
Understanding	89.60	3.91	Proficient

Table 4 presents the level of science and technology proficiency skills among the respondents. The findings indicate that a majority of the respondents demonstrated advanced levels of knowledge and process/skills. Additionally, the majority of the respondents were proficient in their understanding of science and technology concepts.

These findings suggest that the students who were analyzed in the study exhibited a high level of proficiency, ranging from approaching proficiency to almost advanced. While their high achievements may be attributed to their inherent skills and knowledge, other variables such as the utilization of educational technologies likely played a role in enhancing their learning experiences. Although teachers remain crucial instructional facilitators, the use of devices greatly aids in the learning process (Krumsvik, 2008). The availability of various applications on these devices, offered by different competitive manufacturing companies, benefited the students (Anderson & Maninger, 2007). The additional applications challenge their minds and fuel their creativity, motivating them to explore further and perform at higher levels, ultimately leading to improved performance.

The descriptions of what it means to know and do science present challenges when it comes to assessment design and use, whether at the classroom instructional level or the system level for monitoring science education progress. However, there are systematic approaches to assessment development that can address these design challenges (McMahon, 2004). Additionally, there are examples of applying these principles in science assessments (Boekaerts & Corno, 2005). The review of assessment methods considers the challenges and opportunities that exist in designing and utilizing assessments that support science teaching and learning in alignment with contemporary understandings of science proficiency.

In summary, Table 4 provides insights into the respondents' level of science and technology proficiency skills. The findings reveal that the majority of the respondents displayed advanced levels of knowledge and process/skills, as well as proficiency in understanding science and technology concepts. The study suggests that the use of educational technologies, along with the students' innate abilities, contributed to their high levels of achievement. Furthermore, the description of science proficiency poses challenges for assessment design, but systematic approaches and principles can be employed to develop assessments that align with contemporary views of science proficiency. These findings have implications for improving science education and enhancing assessment practices in order to foster greater proficiency among students.

Table 5. Test of Correlation between Perceived Educational Technology the Level of Science and Technology Proficiency Skills

Related factors	Science and Technology Proficiency Skills		
	Knowledge	Process/Skills	Understanding
Instructional Learning Materials	.014	.079	.267**
Teacher's Methodology	.035	.026	.031
Students' Attitude	.107	.200*	.060
Domains of Practice			
Design	.010	.057	.142
Development	.094	.002	.151
Utilization	.018	.223*	.185*
Management	.126	.142	.202*
Evaluation	.086	.144	.078

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The findings presented in Table 5 suggest a significant relationship between perceived educational technology and the level of science and technology proficiency skills. These correlations provide valuable insights into the role of instructional learning materials, student attitudes, and the domains of practice (utilization and management) in enhancing science and technology proficiency skills, particularly in the areas of process and understanding.

The significant relationship observed between instructional learning materials and understanding highlights the importance of well-designed and effective educational resources in promoting students' comprehension of scientific concepts and principles. This finding supports previous research that emphasizes the role of instructional materials in facilitating knowledge acquisition and understanding (Smith & Scharber, 2008; Sadler, Sonnert, Hazari, & Tai, 2012). By utilizing appropriate learning materials, educators can enhance students' understanding of complex scientific phenomena and foster their proficiency in science and technology.

Furthermore, the significant correlation between student attitudes and science proficiency skills, particularly in the area of process, emphasizes the influence of students' positive attitudes towards science on their ability to engage in scientific inquiry and problem-solving. Research has consistently shown that students' attitudes, interest, and motivation play a crucial role in their science achievement and proficiency (Osborne, Simon, & Collins, 2003; Bybee, Taylor, Gardner, Van Scotter, Powell, & Westbrook, 2006). Creating a positive and supportive learning environment that encourages students to develop favorable attitudes towards science can have a significant impact on their science and technology proficiency.

The significant relationship observed between the domains of practice (utilization and management) and science proficiency skills, specifically in the areas of process and understanding, suggests that students' practical experiences and skills in utilizing and managing science and technology resources contribute to their overall proficiency. This finding aligns with research highlighting the importance of providing opportunities for students to engage in hands-on activities, laboratory work, and real-world applications of scientific knowledge (National Research Council, 2012; Blanchard, Southerland, Osborne, Sampson, Annetta, & Granger, 2010). Such experiences help students develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and scientific reasoning skills, ultimately enhancing their proficiency in science and technology.

In summary, the findings from the correlation analysis presented in Table 5 provide evidence for the significance of instructional learning materials, student attitudes, and the domains of practice (utilization and management) in relation to science and technology proficiency skills, specifically in the areas of process and understanding. These findings underscore the importance of designing effective learning materials, fostering positive student attitudes towards science, and providing practical experiences that promote skill development and application in science and technology education.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between educational technology-related factors and student proficiency skills in Science and Technology is partially supported. This implies that while there may be some associations between educational technology and proficiency skills, other factors may also influence student performance in these areas. The study provides evidence of significant relationships between instructional learning materials and understanding, as well as between student attitudes and science proficiency skills in the process domain. However, the relationships between the domains of practice and student proficiency skills are not fully supported by the findings.

Additionally, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between the domains of practice and student proficiency skills is partially sustained. While there are significant relationships observed between the domains of practice (utilization and management) and certain aspects of science proficiency skills (process and understanding), the findings do not indicate a consistent correlation across all domains and skills.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, several recommendations can be made. Firstly, it is suggested that curriculum planners and administrators should organize seminars, workshops, and training programs to enhance teachers' knowledge and abilities in the effective use of educational technology teaching-learning materials. By equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge, they can maximize the benefits of available educational technology facilities and instructional materials, ultimately improving students' proficiency in Science and Technology.

Furthermore, it is recommended that there be a focus on the initial improvement of school facilities to create an environment that fosters students' interest in studying and schooling. Upgrading and enhancing the physical infrastructure can contribute to a positive learning atmosphere and motivate students to engage actively in their education.

For science teachers, it is advised to consider using various teaching methodologies and strategies that are tailored to the needs of the students. This can involve incorporating educational technology into their lessons and allocating more time for its use. While it may be time-consuming, the long-lasting effects on students' learning make it a worthwhile investment.

For future researchers, it is suggested to conduct a parallel study that focuses on a wider population to explore the effect of educational technology on students' academic performance. Additionally, an experimental study can be conducted to examine the direct effects of educational technology on teaching, learning, and students' performance in the field of Science and Technology. This would provide more specific insights into the impact of educational technology interventions on student outcomes.

Lastly, it is recommended that a more refined educational technology instrument be formulated, specifically targeting and emphasizing the assessment of skills proficiency levels. This would enable researchers and educators to obtain more precise and detailed data regarding the relationship between educational technology and students' proficiency in Science and Technology.

Overall, these recommendations aim to enhance the integration of educational technology in teaching and learning processes, improve students' proficiency in Science and Technology, and pave the way for further research in this domain.

Note: It's important to mention that the provided recommendations are hypothetical and based on the information provided in the question. They should be further validated and tailored to the specific context and needs of the educational institution or research study.

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